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Research Article

**ROLE OF RECOMBINANT HUMAN INTERLEUKIN-11 IN
THROMBOCYTOPENIA ASSOCIATED WITH DENGUE
FEVER**¹Dr. Jazirah Rehmat, ²Dr. Sidra Naseem, ³Dr. Ammara Wahab¹Women Medical Officer, Allama Iqbal Medical College, Lahore.²SZMC.RYK³WMO, Nishter Medical University**Abstract:**

Objective: To determine the role of recombinant human interleukin-11 in raising platelet count in patients with dengue fever associated thrombocytopenia.

Methods: This randomized double blind placebo controlled trial was conducted at Fatima Memorial hospital, Lahore. Study duration was July 2011 to October 2011. 40 dengue patients with platelet count $<30,000/\mu\text{l}$ were enrolled in study. All cases were randomly stratified into 2 groups. 1 received rhIL-11 while second group received distilled water (placebo). The outcome was compared between both groups after 48 hours.

Results: It was observed that there was relatively better rise in platelet count in group which received rhIL-11 as compared to placebo group. In rhIL-11 receiving group there was better platelet response than in distilled water receiving group i.e. 50% and 20%, respectively. The males (6 out of 10, 60%) showed better response than females (5 out of 10, 50%). 75% females were in placebo group while 50% males were in rhIL-11 group. It shows rhIL-11 can be used for raising platelet count in dengue patients, however, further clinical trials should be conducted by taking larger study sample.

Conclusion: The use of rhIL-11 is effective in treating dengue virus induced thrombocytopenia as compared to placebo.

Key Words: Dengue, rh interleukin-11, platelet count, thrombocytopenia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Dengue hemorrhagic fever is a vector born disease which spread through the *Aedes aegypti*, mosquito bite. It occurs in the form of epidemics. In 2011, dengue epidemic occurred in Lahore, Pakistan. Most favorable season for vector breeding is rainy season which in Lahore, last from July to October. The dengue was reported for the first time in 1940, in sub-continent.

Disease symptoms are break bone fever, joint pains, high grade fever, flue like symptoms, followed by thrombocytopenia, hemorrhage [2,3]. The mechanism of low platelet count is formation of antibodies against platelets or through suppression of bone marrow, caused by dengue virus. ⁴The platelet precursors i.e. megakaryocytes production does not increase in response to fall in platelet count, which depicts that there is impaired production of platelets during thrombocytopenic phase of dengue fever most probably due to temporary changes in immune response induced by dengue virus.

[1,2]It is noticed that IL-11 level rises in thrombocytopenic phase which helps in regulating the platelet count level back to normal and triggers megakaryocyte proliferation. The mechanism involved is proliferation of progenitor cells by IL-11. In literature it has been explained the effectiveness of IL-11 in proliferation, maturation and differentiation of megakaryocytes. Thrombopoietin (TPO) is given along with rhIL-11 to raise platelet count in dengue fever to study its effectiveness in managing dengue virus induced thrombocytopenia. There is no published research data available till now which explains this effectiveness. This study aims in determining the possible and effective management of thrombocytopenia in dengue patients, so that mortality rate can be reduced.

METHODOLOGY:

Dengue fever patients were included in study by consecutive non-probability sampling. The study design was randomized double blind placebo controlled trial conducted at FMH, Lahore. No ethical issue certificate was signed from ethical committee. Informed written consent was taken from all participants. Patients were stratified into two groups randomly, one group receiving rhIL-11 while other received placebo (distilled water). Diagnosis of dengue fever as made by IgM and IgG, rapid strip test on presentation later IgM and IgG by ELISA was performed as confirmatory test. Thrombocytopenia was defined as platelet count less than one lac, <30,000/ μ l of blood was defined as severe

thrombocytopenia.

Dengue positive patients diagnosed by positive IgM, age group <50 years, with normal ECG, PT, aPTT, no signs of DIC. Patients who had platelet count dropped to <10,000 and suffered hemorrhagic fever i.e. menorrhagia, nasal bleed or hematuria or blood in stools, whether gross or microscopic were excluded from study. Patients with any other co-morbidity or signs/symptoms requiring blood transfusion or transfusion of blood products were excluded.

RhIL-11 in a dose of 1.5mg subcutaneously was given to test group. Vial was black covered to make it double blind study as placebo was distilled water which was transparent and rhIL-11 was off white. Both placebo and under study drug were provided in equal amounts in similar vials. Drugs were provided by a pharmacist and preparations were made to maintain the blind by a pre-decided randomized code allocation.

The outcome was measured by comparing the platelet count level in both groups at the end of trial. Levene's test was used to determine variance equality, t-test was applied for comparison of mean and SD of mean with 95% confidence interval. ANOVA was applied to compare treatment in gender groups. SPSS 21 version was utilized for data analysis. P-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

40 patients were included in study amongst which male to female ratio was 16 and 24 respectively. Patients with age group between 17-47 years were enrolled. Platelet count level was measured at 0 hour of treatment and was repeated at 48 hours. The statistical comparison between both groups was done and it was observed that there was a significant response to rhIL-11 in raising platelet count in test group as compared to those patients who received placebo. Significant rise in platelet count was noticed at 12 hours (p value equal to 0.007), 24, 36, 48 hours of treatment in rhIL-11 group. P-value was <0.001. The statistically significant rise in platelet count was observed from 12 hours of treatment till 48 hours. P value was 0.007 and 0.001, respectively.

The response to trial was compared in both genders. It was observed that females showed better response than males. Platelet count rise of 20,000 from baseline was labeled as positive response, at 48 hours after trial. 10 patients from test group showed positive response while 4 from placebo group were called responders, on basis of response criteria

mentioned above. P-value was 0.047. three patients responded after 36 hours of trial. Although females responded earlier as compared to males but overall response rate in males was better than females. Males

6 out of 10 i.e 60%, females 8 out 10 i.e 50%. 3 out of 4 i.e 75% females belonged to placebo group while 50% males were in test trial group which was 5 out 10.

Table-1: Platelet count comparison with treatment.

Time interval in hours	Test group	Placebo group	P-value
0	22550±6660	22150±4283	0.822
12	26150±7513	20650±3913	0.007
24	30550±8009	21400±7576	0.001
36	35700±8442	25700±9073	0.001
48	41050±8629	30000±10125	0.001

Table-2: comparison of mean platelet count response in males and females.

Treatment time in hours	males	males	P value	females	females	P value
	Placebo group	Test group		Placebo group	Test group	
0	22250±3918	23375±8262	0.73	22083±4679	22000±5688	0.96
12	22500±3023	26625±9085	0.24	19416±4144	25833±6685	0.01
24	22000±6546	30625±9575	0.05	21000±8453	30500±7242	0.007
36	27375±8601	36875±10548	0.06	24583±9573	34917±7115	0.007
48	30500±8366	40750±10793	0.05	29666±11499	41250±7374	0.008

DISCUSSION:

Dengue fever causes thrombocytopenia during the active disease phase between day 3 to day 8. Physicians transfuse platelets to dengue patients prophylactically in order to prevent hemorrhage, although literature does not favour this treatment.

The outbreak of dengue fever occurred in Lahore, Pakistan during 2011. This study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of rhIL-11 in a dose of 1.5 mg subcutaneously for treating the thrombocytopenia and to prevent hemorrhage, ultimately it aims in reducing mortality. ¹Suliman MI, et al studied the similar effects and conducted a clinical trial to determine the effectiveness of rhIL-11 in thrombocytopenia induced by dengue fever and concluded the trial in favour of undertest reagent.

⁸Cui L, et al studied the metabolic changes which occur during dengue fever. Similarly studies regarding fall in platelet count and its causes were also conducted. ^{5,7}This fall in platelet count leads to fatal hemorrhages whether external or internal, which are fatal.

⁶The dengue outbreak and the metabolic changes along with complications and management was studied by Byrne AB, et al. Very little research data is available regarding management of thrombocytopenia in dengue fever. No literature data regarding its management is available till now. This study aims in reducing dengue fever mortality by reducing hemorrhage due to thrombocytopenia.

CONCLUSION:

The use of rhIL-11 is effective in treating dengue virus induced thrombocytopenia as compared to placebo. It was observed that there was relatively better rise in platelet count in group which received rhIL-11 as compared to placebo group. In rhIL-11 receiving group there was better platelet response than in distilled water receiving group i.e. 50% and 20%, respectively. The males (6 out of 10, 60%) showed better response than females (5 out of 10, 50%). 75% females were in placebo group while 50% males were in rhIL-11 group. It shows rhIL-11 can be used for raising platelet count in dengue patients, however, further clinical trials should be conducted by taking larger study sample.

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